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TRANSCENDING THE SPATIO-TEMPORAL CONTINUUM: CONNECTING THROUGH MYTHS AND MEMORIES IN GIRISH KARNAD'S NĀGA-MANDALA

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ABSTRACT

Girish Karnad the veteran Indian playwright is an architect who transformed Indian theatre to a live space for brewing of ideas and emotions, genuinely felt to this day while having their roots into the depths of human psyche from time immemorial. The resonances of Vedas and Upanishads, through folk literature and culture, to the ringing of the note from Eliot's *The Wasteland*, everywhere is a dire urge to connect beneath the lines that float on the surface. History and myths, folklores and tradition, images and archetypes pile one upon the other creating ripples in the mind and psyche. Karnad's plays cross genres even in the form of theatre enacted on stage. The transcendental images evoked in the rejuvenated flames, the female spirits, the darkness that sprouts fears and stories, at once, bring about a world that recreates itself in the spirit of modernity, gathering cinders amidst ashes. The search for completeness, the desire for love, the frenzied emotions, the lurking semblances that appear here and there reveal Karnad's pursuit for the numerous overlapping faces beneath masks. Memories flow in their usual nature and the flow of thoughts break apart the linearity, the burden of tradition. What remains is the flow and the susurrations, the darkness and the shadows, the continuance, the helplessness and the hope.

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Girish Karnad (1938-2019), one of the predominant playwrights from India, who changed the face of theatre in general and Indian stage in particular, has often been regarded to have harboured several transcendental processes in his writing. With innovative techniques on stage, Karnad is known to have let loose the “chaos through [the]... clash between ritual, reality and drama” (*The Book Review*). The characters of Karnad’s plays are both individuals and epochs, speaking their contemporary world and its tradition. Karnad’s characters bear the imprint of tradition in their moves but never carry the same as luggage; tradition is both celebrated and refuted. The plays of Karnad situate themselves in diverse settings, and action to loud thinking are all performed on stage. Karnad dreams and brings myths to connect his dreams to the collective unconscious of a nation, a people, and to the wide human world. The archetype of pain and loss, desire and longing leave a deep sigh of relief as the contemporary events and emotions come to fill this gap.

The resonances of Indian history and culture and nonetheless Western thoughts and notions that he had derived through years of stay in the West, can be heard in Karnad’s plays. Karnad’s thoughts flow without any barriers of time, space or consciousness. K. R. Srinivasa Iyengar while speaking of Karnad’s three plays, *Tughlaq*, *Yayati* and *Hayavadana* writes in his *Indian Writing in English*,

In all his three plays – be the theme historical, mythical or legendary— Karnad’s approach is ‘modern’, and he deploys the conventions and motifs of folk art like masks and curtains to project a world of intensities, uncertainties and unpredictable denouements (735).

Arshia Sattar, the Indian translator and writer to have translated Sanskrit texts as *Kathasaritsagara* and *Valmiki’s Ramayana*, comments on Girish Karnad’s story of life, *This Life at Play: Memoirs*, thus:

...Girish Karnad tells the story of his remarkable life, a life lived so richly and so well. But this is also the story of how a young generation in a newly independent nation forged a language in the arts that challenged tradition and the status quo, that sought to understand and inhabit modernity in their terms (Sattar).

The plays of Karnad primarily centre around the themes of exchange of selves and transformation of subjectivity. The world of love and languish gets transformed to become complicated as subjectivities clash. The two protagonists in the play *Hayavadana* exchange heads and change roles to prove that they are none other than one and the same self divided into two different existences. Karnad has deep insight into the human selves and different personalities in his characters conflate to form one being. On the other hand widely different traits within the same character, creating rift in the personality of a single individual is a common motif in Karnad’s perception. Karnad in his tales of love and hatred, envy and jealousy, creates characters who are unaware of the processes within themselves.

Karnad’s host of plays ponder upon mythical events straitjacketed into his (Karnad’s) understanding of the same from his perspective which is strongly modernist. His plays *Yayati* (1960), *Hayavadana* (1971), *Nāga-Mandala* (1988) and *The Fire and the Rain* (1998) beneath the mythical core which is highly connective in transcending the spatio-temporal continuum evinces a lingering loss which is of this day. The urge to attain completion, fulfilment, wholeness and fruition reveals the void and the dark chasm of human heart. The characters in their own way attempt hard to locate the centre.

Karnad’s first play *Yayati* is based on an episode adopted from the ‘Adiparva’ of the *Mahabharata*. Yayati a king of the Kuru dynasty is given to worldly pleasures and dalliance in love. He is married to Devayani, Sukracharya’s daughter, but in his pursuit of lust he molests Sharmishtha, a close associate of Devayani. This sprouts the vengeful ire of Sukracharya who curses Yayati with old age. Decrepitude which is highly symbolic is however taken over by his son Puru in exchange of his youth. This redemption of the father meted out by the son drags Puru’s wife, Chitrlekha, a character created by Karnad, to suicide. This act ultimately brings about the revelation in Yayati who comes to his senses, out of the lure of sensual pleasures. While Sharmishtha avenges her past humiliation by her body, the three women characters in the play suffer from a sense of exile, within. The dichotomy between satiety and spiritual surrendering is craftily projected as myths form the backdrop to contemporary motifs.

Hayavadana has two stories clubbed into one or the different rift in consciousness has been projected by the piling together of two different identities, the diverse notions of selves into one framework. The man with the horse's head which begins the narrative is complemented by the transportation of the heads of the two friends Devadatta and Kapila. Devadatta is the scholar with a strong mind, whereas Kapila is the able-bodied youth whose metallic body and virulence entices and charms Devadatta's wife Padmini. The two men bound in their love and friendship get separated in their jealousy and love for the lone woman, Padmini. Padmini grows through the narrative and from a wife to a lover, she gains acquisition of her self and the self becomes too powerful to be captured within the barriers of the body; instead wafts into the elements. The three characters, Devadatta, Kapila and Padmini form a group but the unification remains incomplete until the end when the three characters ascend the funeral pyre and the two bodies of both the men are claimed as the bodies of her husband by Padmini.

In *Hayavadana* Devadatta and Kapila are friends, of the same age and both have an affinity for Padmini realized or unrealized. In Karnad's other play *Nāga-Mandala*, which is considered quite similar to *Hayavadana*, Rani gets wedded to Appanna while she finds her love in the character of the Naga who had appeared before her in exactly the same face as her husband. In the frame narrative of *Hayavadana* the man has a horse's head. While the head that nods is that of the horse, the head that speaks is that of the human. The merging of the animal instincts and the human sensibilities, along with a tinge of Lord Ganesha's divinity make for completeness in Girish Karnad's plays.

In *Nāga-Mandala* the Naga reeling in love for Rani, the young adolescent bride takes over the form and countenance of her husband and wins over her love only to be in a deep engagement of love and perfect reciprocation. There are hardly any big or small, prominent or insignificant characters in Karnad. Instead Karnad's characters are steeped in emotions, deep seated and unaware of the self. Love is all, however love is no surrender, instead a terrible urge to possess. The husband to Rani, Appanna though never ever takes heed of his wife and is engaged in a relationship with the concubine of the village, as she is referred to by Kurudavva, becomes steeped in a sense of battered ego as his wife becomes pregnant. However when the entire village stands stunned by the cobra hanging round her neck in the resemblance of a garland, and the entire world of creatures bless her, in spite of the fact that he had never touched his wife, he does not dare speak against her (Rani). He does not even try to find out the truth behind the natural birth of the child and the even more uncanny motherhood. Instead he kneels down before the wrath of nature that he believes had made possible the unnatural as a mark of revenge on him for his tortures.

The village eldermen gather around Rani and claim her as the goddess as soon as the Naga spreads its head upon Rani. Patriarchy though takes the upper hand in judging the chastity of a woman, surrenders before a lame serpent considering it the most powerful, just and true. This incident actually changes the course of the play and brings about the real climax.

In the play *The Fire and the Rain* Karnad also plays upon the theme of man and his duality, his mask, his face and its resemblances. The masks overpower often and the characters do not remain themselves, but often get transformed to become the *other* lurking within the self. In the *Notes to The Fire and the Rain* Karnad writes:

Thus the phrase, *Agni Mattu Malé*, in addition to counterpointing two physical elements normally seen as antagonistic, also sets up several other oppositions: between an Indo-Aryan (Sanskrit) and a Dravidian (Kannada) language, between the pan-Indic and the regional points of view, between the classical 'marga' and the less exalted 'desi' traditions, between the elevated and the mundane, and even perhaps between ...the sacred and the secular ("Notes" *The Fire and the Rain* 63).

Karnad's approach is mythical, and he uses the myth as a psychological pattern which repeats itself. The human mind, as it reciprocates with nature, the inherent feeling of deep oneness between human mind and the primordial nature gets revealed in Karnad's plays. Karnad's plays are an attempt at postcolonial

retaliation and expression of the self. As Anita Myles in *Contemporary Indian English Drama: An Overview* observes:

Girish Karnad extracts the material for his plot from history and mythology mostly but interprets the past in the context of contemporary relevance. (70)

Karnad's myths derived from the Mahabharata (*Yayati* and *The Fire and the Rain*), or *Kathasaritasagara* (*Hayavadana*) or evolving from folklores as in *Nāga-Mandala* are highly functional in projecting themes of contemporary concerns. K. Satchidanandan has rightly pointed out in his *Myth in Contemporary Indian Literature*, "Indian myths in the hands of Girish Karnad prove to be vital, meaningful and inspirational" (189).

The myths project the issues which Karnad brings in to hoist his plots that deal with identity crisis, change of subjects, assertion of female desire in the face of patriarchy, patriarchy's senile attempts to capture the wild moves of the women as powerful as nature and so on. These myths are Karnad's weapons in creating layers and transcending the inhibitions of space and time. The characters evolving from the myths are flesh and blood characters of this day. Karnad deftly carves the myths and frames the characters so as to create a perfect ambience for the projection of the plots.

As Hemandra Nath Das Gupta (*The Indian Theatre*) mentions, from the very beginning of drama, Indian drama had a unique "spirit and structure" (50) of the plays of Bhasa, Kalidasa, etc, we would be sure of the "independent" (50) origin of the Indian theatre. Karnad upholds this spirit and powerfully takes his plots to their fruition. Karnad alters the characters and gives them the dialogue which is spoken by the modern man. Subjectivities clash and identities contest with each other as the characters churn themselves and often stand inward out. As Nandi Bhatia, veteran postcolonial theorist, points out,

Karnad psychologises myth and produces characters with motivations hidden and apparent, transferred and accepted, self-divisions here are not played out within the heroic mode but within existentialist constraints of love. (Bhatia 46-47).

II

Girish Karnad tries to connect between life and the earth through his plays. The processes of human psyche, the human existence are marked by human's proximity with nature and the earth. The earthen as humans are, their existence is often given a deep nudge by the primordial. Often humans prove shallow in their understanding and their lives lose the depth of sensation which is however present in nature. As in his play *Yayati*, so too in *Hayavadana*, *Fire and the Rain* or in *Nāga-Mandala*, everywhere is a dire attempt at studying man's basic instincts and tracing a connection between the human mind and the primordial. The character of Naga in *Nāga-Mandala*, often associated with the fascination of the human mind, is also an emblem of the earth, the coils of the snake is symbolic of rumination and the unwinding journey of life.

The story begins and the story is of a young girl Rani who gets wedded to a man who doesn't love her and instead beats her up. The simple story of several girls from different corners of Indian villages takes a turn as a snake comes to her rescue, a Naga, who gives up the slithering form of a reptile to stand up erect as a human form. The Naga takes the resemblance of Rani's husband Appanna (which reads as any man). Kappanna, another youth of the village, is the "dark one" (*Nāga-Mandala* "Characters") (who first tells his mother Kurudavva, the blind aged lady about Rani's presence in the locked room. This in a way propels the action and invites the snake into Rani's room in a frenzy of love as Kurudavva administers a potion to Rani to incite love in her husband, which unknowingly falls upon the snake.

The Naga or the serpent has numerous connotations when it comes to human psyche. Often judged as the sensual, charged sexually, potent in reproducing and an intricate element of nature, the Naga has often been perceived as a mythical creature who changes forms and dances and becomes human, temporarily discarding its animal existence. Connecting between both the worlds, the snakes though reptiles without limbs and higher functions of the higher animals, often replace humans and vie with them for love and consummation.

In their burning desire and reaching out to their mates in love, in their urgency the snakes grow and are manifested as humans. The Naga in an all-human world is nothing but a mere prey in the hands of men. But in his transformation from the reptile to a big statured man who becomes not only Rani's husband but her child's father is celebrated the regenerative power of love.

The characters in *Nāga-Mandala* overlap one another, and as Appanna, Kappanna and Naga stand before us we realize almost the three-tier structure of the mind as revealed in Freud's hypothesis as the three characters. The characters resemble the reality principle, Appanna; the morality principle in Kappanna as he provides vision to his blind mother and designates the right path; and Naga, the pleasure principle, who is all desire and a genial current of the soul which connects every living to an urge for continuance through interaction with the other. In this play also lies the predominant note that the *other* in humans and animals, serpent, and the marginalized in man can come together and reciprocate in love and desire.

The three characters form the entire of a self, a human mind and in the end we realize that Rani, the slip of a girl gets the realization of her desires and motherhood, through the intervention of these three characters into her life. While Appanna marries Rani, and brings her from her parents' place it is Kappanna who is made to peep into her room to find out whether she had at all attained the status of a wife, is happy and satisfied or is yet to attain the succour of life through this marriage. Under such a condition Rani meets her saviour Kurudavva, only after her son Kappanna tells his mother of her status. It is Kappanna who with Kurudavva form a complete vision amidst night's darkness and the blank vision of Kurudavva.

This intricate connection between the human world and the world of snakes gets repeated in human imagination and is widely scripted in the myths and folklores; on fairy tales and stories. The world of immense possibilities transcends the strict parameters of life and journey into the unseen sphere of interaction between humans and nature of which the snakes form an intricate part. The Naga tries to connect between the human world and instincts of love in animals or lesser creatures which bring them close to human existence. As humans lose their humane feelings, the animals come in to fill the void.

The characters in *Nāga-Mandala* are divided into two sets. The play begins with a frame narrative, where the story, is given the form of a character with a beautiful saree on, which has been transformed into a song. They had left the house of an old woman who had possessed the story and the song within her, but had never revealed them to the world, being unjust to the story and the song, who ultimately take their revenge upon her in their own way. The story and the song enter a desolate temple where burnt out flames used to come and gather, creating space for newer happenings and newer stories. The stories step into a new world of storytelling, where stories and songs come together and create a world all their own.

In this place arrives a story-writer, a creative artist in search of a story, whose advent gives the setting a form, the stories, an audience and the oral form of stories a promise of a written stature. The stories in the process lose their nebulous airy stature and enter into a domain that would be all restricted and controlled by the storyteller. However the coming together of the story and the story-teller is obvious, for one stands awaiting the other.

In *Nāga-Mandala* Karnad designs three endings which leave enough scope for accommodating both Appanna and Naga. The second ending in which the Naga dies is replaced with the ending in which the Naga exists as an intricate part of Rani's existence, her hair. Naga remains in Rani's child, but more so he lives in her satiated desires, her fulfilment, womanhood and motherhood. If Rani's existence is fixed on her husband Appanna, the journey in which she started her life as a wife, a woman, rather than a girl, began with the Naga and his love for her.

In the end Kappanna vanishes in an unknown world where the presence of the Yaksha woman lurks. Nothing is known of him and Karnad does not unravel the story of his vanishing as he claims a different narrator with a separate story awaits the listeners yet to be, with Kappanna's story. While Veena Noble Dass, a veteran critic believes that Karnad had been influenced by Brecht, Anouilh, Camus, Sartre and to a considerable extent, Pinter (17), Aparna Bhargava Dharwadker believes, it is also the classical tradition that mingled to

create Karnad's unique style and technique.

Kappanna is lost and the Naga relegated to the background, becoming an excess in Rani's life. Both these characters the Naga and Kappanna, enter into the recesses of life, seeping through the interstices of this world making myth and miracle possible. Love and lovelessness, fancy and imagination, hope and hopelessness and life beyond this world becomes possible only through the presence of the dark creatures slithering beneath the world of firm, big creatures making moves and exploiting the world and its darknesses.

The Naga merely completes the cycle by responding with his senses, by becoming exactly as Rani's heart desires. Naga's emotions reciprocate with Rani's urges and what emerges is pure bliss. The magical effect of conjugality unfurls in full bloom as both the hearts come together. Naga simply reciprocates Rani's feelings, and Naga is no human, not with frailties, but only love and feelings of purity for Rani which seem idyllic.

The ideal is sought and found but such perfection can only be possible in dream-reality. Immediately we are reminded that it is a story and what ensues is a series of narratives that are not grounded in reality, but merely images, the ideal synchronically arranged. The three characters though different in their presences make mirror images of each other as they are of the same age and while Kappanna is Kurudavva's son, Appanna is almost a son to Kurudavva. The Naga on the other hand exactly resembles Appanna, though holding a shadowy form and entity.

The characters again and again repeat themselves, whether in their similar appearances or in their attitudes. Appanna brings disgrace upon Rani but is rectified by the Naga. Through the presence of the snake the human (Rani) attains her dignity and even her life, for it is the snake which prevents her from facing humiliation before the village elders. The repetitive characters stand back-to-back forming a complete self away from the fractured entities. What comes out is a series of opposites—dark and fair within the same individual (Kappanna, which means dark, while he is actually fair), vision and blindness, day and night, snake and mongoose, love and no-love, the weak and strong (Appanna), the Naga's poison to kill (the dog and the mongoose), and the love to heal.

The three characters, Appanna, Naga and Kappanna as if in a dream get displaced from their single entity of one self who is Rani's husband possessing the qualities of the Naga and embracing the darkness of Kappanna and featuring them in the three different characters. They are actually traits of the same personality who had been conceived in Rani's dreams—"I am convinced I am seeing something with these eyes of mine, only to wake up and find I was dreaming..".(*Nāga-Mandala* 1)

Rani, the young girl imagines herself the queen possessing the best of qualities and dreams of a husband who would love her and care for her to the utmost possible extent. Rani's daydreams meet their downfall as Appanna moves out of the house locking her in, only to return everyday for lunch and dissolving into a state of non-existence. Under such a condition her dreams bring about her wish fulfilment. The completion in Rani's life is brought about by the presence of different creatures from the initial beginning of the play as the whale comes to her rescue and the eagle, and the Naga after them. The characters are brought to the reality's plane and as if given human action in dream-narrative. As extracted from Sigmund Freud's "Dream Work"—

...it is as a rule like a piece of breccia, composed of various fragments of rock held together by a binding medium, so that the designs that appear on it do not belong to the original rocks imbedded in it. And there is in fact one part of the dream-work, known as 'secondary revision,' whose business is to make something whole and more or less coherent out of the, first products of the dream-work (251).

The identities of the three characters merge at times and dissociate at others. While the Naga is active during the night, Appanna can be seen during the day and not at night. Kappanna comes to look at Rani to find out if there had been anybody in the room only to find that Rani was inside. However Kappanna vanishes and Naga subsides as Appanna takes charge of Rani, and holds the centre-stage. All these characters as if grow out of Rani's dream of escape, of movement beyond the tortures of her new-found life. The characteristics of dream as condensation and displacement can both be clearly evinced in the growth and development of the three

characters— Appanna, Kappanna and Naga. The three characters as if in a dream vision are merged together and displace at different levels. These three characters are in away the different strata of the mind.

Karnad handled the myths for the contemporary issues as deftly as sculptor chiselling out voluminous stories on the face of a dead rock. Girish Karnad with Mohan Rakesh, Vijay Tendulkar, Badal Sircar, et al added that unique flavour that stunned the world. His dramas have a cadence as if one can hear the footsteps of God, or prowling beasts, demons or Naga, but strikingly original in its struggles of modern day human clan. As Nandi Bhatia claims in *Modern Indian Theatre*, that the post-colonial Indian theatre “sought to project both modernity and Indianness in its style and subject matter” (xvi) and that Girish Karnad was “reshaping” (46) “mythic material” “around modernist concerns” (46).

The dark tresses of Rani, from the very beginning act as the mark of her beauty. She appears as the snake-woman in her perfect synchronization with the Naga. At the end of the play the Naga is harboured in Rani’s tresses. The sway of Rani’s hairs match the sway of the hood of the cobra. Appanna and Naga on the other hand bear the resemblance of Indra, the most popular deity and Vritra, the serpent, who is his brother, being fathered by his father Tvastri, the Creator of the Universe. Appanna and Naga are similar yet face the same confrontation as the mortal combat of Indra and Vritra. Everywhere is a repetition and a blurring out identities through a piling of images, selves and subjectivities. As E.V. Ramkrishnan and Udaya Kumar, rightly judges—

A perplexing diversity of languages, communities and literary cultures, the continued life of oral traditions and uneven levels of literacy, and complexities of political and economic realities in postcolonial India confront attempts to chart modernism’s career in India. The category itself is Protean, displaying multiple meanings and accents in various regions and contexts; (Ramkrishnan and Kumar).

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